
**PRINCIPALS' ADMINISTRATIVE PRACTICE OF
COLLABORATION AND TEACHERS' JOB PERFORMANCE IN
PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOL IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA**

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Abstract

The study examined how principals' administrative practice of collaboration predicts the job performance of teachers in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The Transformational Leadership Theory was used to guide the study. One research question and a corresponding null hypothesis were formulated to guide the study. A correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population consisted of 254 school principals and 7,388 teachers of the public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State. The sample was 739 teachers from the three Senatorial Districts, selected through the clustered sampling technique. Two research instruments tagged "Principals' Administrative Practice of collaboration Questionnaire" (PAPCQ) and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ)" were used for data collection. The instruments were validated by three experts from the Faculty of Education, University of Uyo. The questionnaires were administered and the data generated in this study were analysed using Simple Linear Regression analysis. The research hypothesis was tested at a .05 level of significance. The results showed that principals' administrative practice of collaboration significantly predicts teachers' job performance in lesson preparation, lesson delivery, classroom management, use of instructional materials and students' assessment in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that school principals should do everything humanly possible to build a team through emphasis and

encouragement on the spirit of teamwork. This is important because a collaborative effort of each member of staff leads to the attainment of the objectives of organizations. Likewise, the Ministry of Education and State Secondary Education Board should as a matter of priority ensure that schools principals are selected based their efficiency in personnel administration and not just based on years of service for the smooth and effective administration of the public secondary schools.

Keywords: *Job Performance, Collaboration, Linear Regression Analysis, Lesson Delivery.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Musselwhite (2007) described a team as a small number of people with complementary skills who are; committed to a common purpose, performance goals, and approach for which they hold themselves mutually accountable. A team can be defined as a group of people coming together to achieve a purpose or common goal. Collaboration can be explained as the ability to work with others through cooperation and communication to accomplish a common goal (Baker, Salas, King, Battles and Barach, 2005). For collaboration to be effective, members must understand the team's purpose, work toward that purpose, and be both independent of and dependent on other members to accomplish the task (Baker et al., 2005). According to Leonard and Leonard (2001), professional collaboration is provided when teachers and administrators work together, share their knowledge, contribute ideas, and develop plans to reach educational and organizational goals.

Anderson and Wahlstrom (2004) opine that collaborating with other schools is a new leadership dimension of school administration. It needs to be acknowledged as a specific role for the educational leaders. It can generate advantages to the school systems as a whole rather than just the students belonging to a single school. But the administrators need to develop their skills to get involved in matters beyond their school.

According to Jay (2014), teachers' job performance is the ability of teachers to combine relevant inputs for the enhancement of teaching and learning processes. Bolarinwa (2016) observes that, the indicator of teachers' job performance is evaluated in the teachers' ability to make a deliberate effort to enhance students' academic performance, possession and display of in-depth knowledge of subject matter, lesson presentation, effective classroom organization and control, and participation in the school curriculum activities. Other indicators of teachers' job performance according to the author include regularity and punctuality in the school, maintenance of good interpersonal relationship with subordinates and superiors, discipline, motivation, and

counseling of students as well as compliance to teachers' professional codes of conducts among others. In other words, teachers' job performance is the degree to which teachers successfully accomplish their instructional responsibilities. A teacher can be said to have performed when the teacher plans his/her lessons according to standards, delivers lessons comprehensively, manages the classroom well, uses instructional materials to facilitate teaching, carries out formative and summative assessments regularly, keep records of students' progress, participates in sporting activities as well as all other functions of the school for the attainment of the set goals of the school.

Efanga (2001) opines that teachers should establish effective classroom climate, students' motivation, management of materials and supplies, physical conditions for instruction, use of time, routines and a monitoring system in the classroom for efficient instruction and quality education. Also, Adeyemi (2011) asserted that variables of job performance such as teaching, lesson notes preparation, effective use of scheme of work, supervision, monitoring of students works and disciplinary ability are virtues which teachers are to uphold to school system. Adeyemi further pointed out that, in this regard, the teachers' performance can be measured through annual reports of activities in terms of the above variables.

Considering the opinion of stakeholders that the country's secondary education is in crisis, many efforts have been made by researchers to probe into issues related to the teaching and learning process, especially at this level. Unfortunately, their efforts have not yielded the desired result despite the innumerable researches conducted and recommendations made with the intention of solving the problem of falling standard of education. Accusing fingers from different quarters are therefore pointed to the government, principals, teachers as well as students as being responsible for the decline in the standard of education at the secondary school level.

Embarrassingly, in most public secondary schools, teachers and principals work in isolation, without any reasonable effort toward teamwork. The spirit of individualism and selfishness are the order of the day. Moreover, unnecessary competition and rivalry among teachers in the same department for personal recognition threaten the existence of the collaborative efforts required for the attainment of the goals for which the schools are established.

It becomes pertinent therefore to ask, "Could the lack of the spirit of teamwork among teachers and the principals be an impediment to principals' administrative practices in public secondary schools?" This question is apt because teachers and principals are the key drivers in secondary schools and so, the success and /or failure of the schools depends greatly on their collaborative

efforts which will lead to good administration by the principals and effective job performance on the part of the teachers. It is against this background that the researchers decided to investigate how principals' administrative practices of collaboration predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. In other words, what is the extent to which principals' administrative practices of collaboration predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

The study was designed to examine the extent to which principals' administrative practice of collaboration predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

The following research question emanates:

To what extent does principals' administrative practice of collaboration predict teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

From the above research question, the following captures the research hypothesis:

The extent to which principals' administrative practice of collaboration predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, is not significant.

The scope of this study covered all the public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria during the 2020/2021 academic year which ended in July 2021. The investigation centered on the principals' administrative practice of collaboration. Job performance of teachers was measured in terms of lesson preparation, lesson delivery, use of instructional materials, classroom management, and students' evaluation in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Transformational Leadership Theory-Bass, J. M. (1985)

Bass (1985) defined transformational leadership in terms of how the leader affects followers, who are intended to trust, admire and respect the transformational leader. Bass identified three ways in which leaders transform followers as:

- i. Increasing their awareness of task importance and value.
- ii. Getting them to focus on team or organizational goals, rather than their own interests.
- iii. Activating their higher-order needs.

Transformational leaders recognize the needs of organization and staff and also stimulate and provide higher level needs inside a person. Transformational leader encourages people to be unified in order to pursuit higher goals with the aim of a positive important change in an organization.

Bass (1985) noted that authentic transformational leadership is grounded in moral foundations that are based on four components namely:

I. Idealized influence: Leaders become model for their followers by their friendly behavior. They admire, respect, and trust their followers. They pay more attention to the needs of their followers than their own needs, and avoid using the power for personal interests. In other words, the leader instils a sense of pride and honor to members to connect with others, show a sense of power and competence, act in a way to rise other's respect and sacrifices personal interest for other's interest.

ii. Inspirational motivation: Inspirational and motivational leaders are those who challenge their followers in their jobs and create a clear perspective to reach goals and go toward the future by increasing efficiency in the workplace. Leaders here talk optimistically about the future, emphasize seriously on things that should be done, talk emphatically about the importance of foresight and raise the hope of members about achievement of goals.

iii. Intellectual stimulation: Leaders encourage their subordinates to try to create motivation and creativity by modifying approaches and opportunities of their own subordinates. The main purpose of the leader is offering free flow of ideas and imaginations so that their followers and subordinates try to reach new techniques and approaches. Here, leaders carefully examine offers to ensure their suitability, take into consideration different perspectives while solving a problem, request for examination of problems from different perspectives and suggest new ways on how to do something.

iv. Personal considerations: Leaders see subordinates more from the individual point of view than a group. They try to influence individual contributions to the organization with the belief that if every individual contributes meaningfully to the system, the attainment of the goals of the organization is surely guaranteed. Leaders allocate time for guidance and training, consider people with different needs, abilities and creativities and help others to develop their capabilities.

This theory is relevant to administrative leadership practices since the main tasks of principals are to motivate, influence, stimulate teachers and to help them develop their teaching skills. Moreover, the principals' carry out administrative leadership practices on persons with divergent opinions, beliefs

and understanding. As such, the concept of individualized consideration as proposed by Bass in his transformational leadership theory is highly relevant to administrative practice of collaboration

2.2 Principals' Collaboration and Teachers' Job Performance

As administrative leaders, principals are in a unique position to influence collaboration that takes place among teachers. In order to create a collaborative environment for teachers, principals should have deep knowledge, skills about professional learning communities and initiation to realize it. In this respect, Murphy, Smylie, Mayrowetz and Louis (2009) argue that distributed leadership helps them change instructional practices. In order to create a collaborative environment, school principals must group teachers into effective teams for effective collaboration, believe in the inherent ability of teachers to serve in leadership capacities, provide, encourage and expect participation opportunities for staff involvement in important decisions, empower leadership teams to make decisions and encourage risk-taking. By creating collaborative learning communities or teams, teachers benefit from the insights of their colleagues, which offers good source for their own professional capacity.

According to Leonard and Leonard (2001) professional collaboration is provided when teachers and administrators work together, share their knowledge, contribute ideas, and develop plans to reach educational and organizational goals. In practice, collaborative practice is exemplified when school staff members come together on a regular basis in their continuing attempts so that their students can become more successful learners. In this respect, Senge, Cambron-McCabe, Lucas, Smith, Dutton & Kleiner (2000) claims that if principals become the “lead teacher and lead learner”, they can move beyond traditional leadership styles to create professional learning communities. The basic goal here is to develop people at school. Teachers must be comfortable to challenge their own and others' assumptions and beliefs within safe places to learn together at school, (Thompson, Gregg and Niska, 2004). Various strategies are employed by administrators in an attempt to foster teacher collaboration; key actions include promoting a shared vision, visibility, providing individual and team feedback, attending and/or facilitating meetings, and monitoring team progress through the use of student achievement data (Balyer, Karatas and Alcia, 2015)

Musselwhite (2007), defined a team as a small number of people with complementary skills who are; committed to a common purpose, performance goals, and approach for which they hold themselves mutually accountable. A team can be defined as a group of people coming together to achieve a purpose or common goal. In the workplace, teams change and grow. One way to have

successful teams is to incorporate team building into the workplace. To Kennett (2007), a team is a group of people who have a task that demanded a high level of interdependency. In other words, they have a goal that can be accomplished only as a team. They need to have boundaries to create cohesion and sustainability among members.

Collaboration usually refers to a series of activities that improves the performance of a team by strengthening the relationships among team members. Collaboration might involve many different exercises and activities. Although the different activities could lead to different results, in the end, collaboration is effective in building relationships and helping performance (Hunter, 2007). Collaboration creates trust and cooperation among team members. When engaging in team building activities, team members complete interactive activities and discussions in order to encourage teamwork. Collaboration works in school settings, work environments, sports, and other recreational activities. Teams are a formal way to actualize collaboration, which is at the heart of successful decision making. Team building is a way to formalize the power of collaboration among staff by blending the talents. Team building is a process of awareness building. It helps staff understand that the sum is greater than the parts and that their decisions would be better if they worked together as a team. “Collaboration is a culture, team building is a value, a mission, a deep down belief in the participants' soul to like and love their job as well as their co-workers” (Cardus, 2007)

Strong, effective working teams can greatly impact and increase staff productivity, employee morale, and overall staff retention rates. There is a need for team building in most workplaces, including schools. School faculty must have tools in order to set goals and objectives. In the workplace, everything is fast-paced and ever changing. It is expected that people in the workplace could work together effectively and get along with one another while simultaneously moving toward achieving a common goal. Due to these expectations, it becomes necessary to have methods in place to assist in team building.

“The most important feature of a successful team is high morale” (Protheroe, 2006). When implementing team-building activities in the workplace, it is necessary to establish objectives and provide training in how to work together. One important part of building a successful team is the ability to keep morale high among the members of the team. Morale is tied to factors such as support, resources, communication, and the personalities involved. A leader should select a team-building activity that would be good for the team. Some of the best team- building activities are the worst team-building experiences when there is no clear objective. Leaders should begin with a clear objective in mind. The goal should be attainable for the team, relevant, applicable to the team's

abilities, and reinforced long after completion of the activity. Leaders who implement team building with their employees should be prepared for their activities and certain that everyone would have a positive learning experience. Leaders should read the exercises, obtain all necessary materials, set up the room, and anticipate potential problems (Miller and Miller, 2001).

Team-building techniques can be put into place to improve an organization. Successful team building creates effective, focused work teams. To help design a team oriented environment, Heathfield (2007) created the Twelve C's for team building to foster continuous improvement including total quality, lean manufacturing, and self-directed work teams. Successful team building that creates effective, focused work teams requires attention to each of the Twelve C's. The Twelve C's are:

- I. **Clear Expectations:** Leaders clearly communicate their expectations for the team's performance and expected outcome. Team members understand why the team is created.
- ii. **Context:** Team members need to understand why they are participating on teams and that forming the team will help the organization attain its communicated goals. The team understands where its work fit in the total context of the organization's goals, principles, visions, and values.
- iii. **Commitment:** Team members need to want to be part of the team and to feel the mission is important. The team members are excited about working together on the goals of the team.
- iv. **Competence:** The team has the appropriate people participating with the knowledge, skill, and capability to address the issues for which the team is formed.
- v. **Charter:** The team assumes responsibility and designs its own mission, vision, and strategies to accomplish the mission.
- vi. **Control:** The team has freedom and is empowered to feel the ownership necessary to accomplish its task.
- vii. **Collaboration:** The team understands team and group processes and the stages of group development. Team members work together effectively. Team members understand the roles and responsibilities of team members and team leaders.
- viii. **Communication:** Team member are clear about their tasks. The team knows the complete context for their existence and communicates clearly and honestly with each other.
- ix. **Creative Innovation:** The organization is interested in change and values creative thinking, unique solutions, and new ideas. The team rewards people who take reasonable risks to make improvements. Administrators provide training, education, access to books and films, and field trips necessary to stimulate new thinking.

- x. Consequences: Team members need to be responsible and accountable for the team achievements. Reasonable risk is respected and encouraged in the organization. Team members spend time resolving problems and can see their impact on increased organizational success.
- xi. Coordination: Teams are coordinated by a central leadership team that assists the groups in obtaining what they needed for success. Priorities and resource allocation are planned across departments.
- xii. Cultural Change: The organization recognizes that the team-based, collaborative, empowering, enabling, organizational culture of the future is different from the traditional, hierarchical organization. (Heathfield, 2007)

Team-building methods in corporations generally refers to the selection and motivation of teams for fulfillment of organizational goals. Corporate team-building techniques aid people in adapting to new requirements. Team-building skills are critical for a person's effectiveness as a manager or as an effective member of a corporate team. Kidd (2007) provided basic methods for team building. The first was to have diversity of skills and personalities. When all members of the team contributed their full strengths, they compensated for each other's weaknesses. When implementing team building, it is critical to have good communication and harmony among the team members.

Whether in education, sports, or business, the right components are needed to build a successful team. Lee (2007) developed seven key components in building a successful team, as follows: i. Find the right team members. They need to be able to accomplish their goal. ii. Give each person in the team a valued role. Everyone is important and needs to have a valued role to feel ownership. This helps create a sense of self-esteem in the individual. iii. Create a unique identity for the team. Let the team decide on a nickname. It will give them confidence. Success is all about confidence. iv. Commit to excellence. The people on a successful team must have the drive to succeed. They should perform and execute tasks with pride. v. Give them a vision. A vision motivates employees. vi. Play or work with passion. Everyone on the team should love what he or she is doing. They are proud of their expertise. vii. Get out of the way. Leaders may just have to “give them the ball” and get out of their way. Let the team do its own thing. The business climate is becoming more complex and businesses needed to adapt to change with agility.

In summary, the principals' administrative role in creating a collaborative culture has been recognized as a prerequisite for school leaders and there appears to be a robust relationship between such leaders and successful collaboration in schools. This review has identified some specific strategies that have been utilized in nurturing a collaborative environment.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample for this study was 739 teachers from the three senatorial districts (the thirty three Local Government Area) which formed 10% of teachers of Akwa Ibom State. The sample was selected through the clustered sampling technique where the state was grouped into the three Senatorial Districts. 10% of the total number of teachers in each of the three Senatorial Districts was further selected as sample through simple random sampling. Three students were also randomly selected to provide information on each teacher's job performance from each of the three Senatorial Districts in Akwa Ibom.

3.2 Instrumentation

Two instruments named Principals' Administrative Practice of Collaboration Questionnaire (PAPCQ) and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ) were used to collect data from respondents (Teachers and students)

3.3 Method of Data Analysis

The data generated in this study were analyzed using Simple Linear Regression analysis for research questions and null hypotheses. The hypothesis was tested at a .05 level of significance.

4. FINDINGS

4.1 Answering the Research Question

Research Question: To what extent does principals' administrative practice of collaboration predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria?

To answer this research question, Simple Linear Regression analysis was employed, and the data obtained are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Simple linear regression analysis for the extent to which principals' collaboration predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary school in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria..

Variable	R	R Square	Extent of Prediction	Remark
Principals' Collaboration(x)	.564	.318	31.7%	Weak Extent
Teachers' Job Performance(y)				

Source: Researcher's Computation.

The entry in Table 1 reveals the R for the strength of the relationship and R² for the determination of the extent to which principals' collaboration predicts teachers' job performance. The R-Value of .564 indicates the extent to which the prediction occurs. The calculated R² of .318 which is the coefficient of determinant indicates that only 31.7% variability in effectiveness is predicted or contributed by principals' collaboration. This implies that principals' collaboration to a weak extent, predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

4.2 Testing the Research Hypothesis

Hypothesis: - The extent to which principals' administrative practice of collaboration predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, is not significant.

Table 2: Simple linear regression analysis for the prediction between principals' collaboration and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Source of Variation	Sum of square	df	Mean square	F-cal	Sig
Regression	48909.902	1	48909.902	342.703	.000 ^b
Residual	104897.720	735	142.718		
Total	153807.623	736			

Source: Researchers' Computation.

The entries in Table 2 revealed that the calculated F-value of 342.70 is greater than the critical F-value of 3.86 at .05 level of significance with 1 and 736 degrees of freedom. With this result, the null hypothesis which claims that the extent to which principals' collaboration predicts teachers' job performance is not significant is rejected. The result reveals that principals' collaboration significantly predicts teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

4.3 Discussion of finding

The result shows that there is significant prediction between principals' collaboration and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. This result means that principals' ability to relate freely with staff, accept advice from teachers when taking decisions, hold regular staff meetings and encourage teamwork among teachers contributes to a weak extent to teachers' job performance.

According to Balyera, Karatas and Alci (2015), in education, teachers' individual and collective efforts are essential in order to improve students'

learning and realize reforms successfully. The researchers postulated that capacity development is very important at schools. Balyera et al. stated further that capacity development is a complicated state based on motivation, skill development, learning, positive organizational culture and support mechanisms. It is believed that establishing professional learning communities develops capacity and improves students' learning at school. Studies have concluded that collaboration can help teachers balance strengths and weaknesses as they meet a varied level of student needs and ultimately improve student achievement outcomes (Markow, Pieters, & Harris Interactive, 2010). Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2017) also found that a supportive and collaborative atmosphere at work could be associated with lower attrition rates. According to Van Der Mescht and Tyala (2008), successful principals support teamwork by establishing a cohesive climate in which team members from distinctive backgrounds with various areas of expertise collaborate to reach a shared goal. When principals facilitate successful teams by focusing on a wide variety of skills, teachers become part of teams with a comprehensive range of ideas, expertise, and experiences that can be shared and reflected upon.

Hord (2007) described one of the major outcomes of teachers' collaboration as learning that informs classroom practice and forges new knowledge and thinking about teachers and learners. Similarly, Hollins, McIntyre, DeBose, Hollins and Towner (2004) found that teacher collaboration evoked a strategic focus to the problem of low achieving students, allowing them to envision a new approach and innovative instruction. Nevertheless, collaboration is widely misunderstood, and the anti-collaborative culture is pervasive within schools. In other words, it is not easy to establish a collaborative culture with teachers who prefer to work in isolation (Rasberry, Mahajan, & Center for Teaching Quality, 2008). Moreover, principals who cultivate teamwork will establish a culture of trust and openness, in which teachers feel a sense of shared values and purpose, feel safe to express their feelings, enjoy acknowledgement for their accomplishments, and know they are buffered against negative external forces (Duyar, Gumus, and Bellibas, 2013)

In order to create a collaborative environment, Murphy, Smylie, Mayrowetz and Louis (2009) suggest that school principals must group teachers into effective teams for effective collaboration, believe in the inherent ability of teachers to serve in leadership capacities, provide, encourage and expect participation opportunities for staff involvement in important decisions, empower leadership teams to make decisions and encourage risk-taking. According to Leonard and Leonard (2001) professional collaboration is provided when teachers and administrators work together, share their knowledge, contribute ideas, and develop plans to reach educational and organizational goals. In practice, collaborative practice is exemplified when

school staff members come together on a regular basis in their continuing attempts so that their students can become more successful learners.

Team building is a way to formalize the power of collaboration among staff by blending the talents. Team building is a process of awareness building. It helps staff understand that the sum is greater than the parts and that their decisions would be better if they worked together as a team. “Collaboration is a culture, team building is a value, a mission, a deep down belief in the participants' soul to like and love their job as well as their co-workers” (Cardus, 2007). On final note, Aladenusi and Ayodele (2011) asserted that a collaborative effort between the principal and teachers will improve service delivery in schools.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended among other things that school

principals should do everything humanly possible to build a team through emphasis and encouragement on the spirit of teamwork. This is important because a collaborative effort of each member of staff leads to the attainment of the objectives of organizations. School principals who desire to be successful in their administrative duties should be able to effectively manage the staff under their leadership. The principals should be approachable, empathetic, recognize and appreciate good performance, criticize constructively, encourage staff development among other things. The office of a good school principal should be accessible to all including the students.

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